

SIMULATIVE DESIGN OF OVERBRAIDED PRESSURE VESSEL FOR HYDROGEN STORAGE

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1 Introduction

Hydrogen is considered to be an alternative fuel for future automotive generations. In pressure vessels made of fiber-reinforced composites it can be stored efficiently under high working pressure of typically 70 MPa. Nowadays, these vessels are produced using filament winding. This paper will examine the braiding process as an alternative approach. Based on finite element modeling a filament wound and a braided pressure vessel are optimized for minimal weight. Particularly, the different fiber orientations and laminate thickness are taken into consideration. With the help of existing models for the winding process, the braided structure is evaluated in an analog way but with regard to its characteristic technological restrictions. It is evident that both laminate structure and vessel contour have to be modified to ensure acceptable structural performance.

2 Motivations

The market for composites pressure vessels is expected to grow at an annual growth rate of 13.8 %. Most composite vessels are manufactured via filament winding, which can be time consuming [1]. State of the art is to produce such pressure vessels in small quantities by use of the wet filament winding process. As structural materials carbon fibers and thermoset matrix are used. To ensure that these pressure vessels stay attractive in comparison to alternative energy storage systems, improvements in design as well as in production techniques for composites are essential.

The braiding process combined with resin-transfer molding (RTM) is an alternative production

approach, which has the potential to decrease cycle times and thus allowing a higher productivity for serial production. Former work could prove that by placing a carbon fibre braid over an aluminum liner, followed by an injection of resin via resin transfer molding significantly faster cycle times can be achieved. Braids have lower strength values compared to unidirectional composites but show superior failure mechanism [2, 6].

Effective modeling strategies for pressure vessels should include the simulation of the manufacturing process to take decisive factors for product performance and reliability into account. Concerning filament wound vessels this is considered to be state-of-the-art [3, 4].

Fig. 1. Filament winding simulation [4]

For braided pressure vessels effective modeling strategies are still to be developed, especially with regard to taking the manufacturing process into account for the structural design. In particular local fiber orientation and laminate thickness are of interest. Furthermore the optimization of the vessel geometry in terms of feasible placement paths of the braiding fibers is important.

3 Methods

To examine the previous mentioned aspects, a calculation model for design of overbraided pressure vessels is developed. This is done in an analog way to the well-established procedure of simulating filament wound pressure vessels.

Braiding gained attention for applications in composite manufacturing due to its high productivity while allowing complex shapes and load-specific tailoring of the fiber architecture [8]. To form a braid at least three fiber strands (tows/rovings) are needed. These strands are crossed over each other. It is a classic textile process, which has been adapted to the characteristics of brittle technical fibers like carbon with a modification called the radial braiding.

The radial braiding machine RF 1/144-100 from Herzog is used to produce braided preforms at the Institute for Textiltechnik (ITA) of RWTH Aachen University. Up to 144 fiber strands can be placed onto a mandrel simultaneously. The radial overbraiding machine consists of a machine bed equipped with horn gears. These horn gears guide the bobbins with the carbon fiber strands around the center of the machine, thereby interlacing the fiber strands. The carbon fibers are guided over a braiding ring onto a braiding core. An industrial robot supports and controls the movement of this core.

Fig. 2. Left: Radial braiding machine; right: process guiding for overbraiding of pressure vessel

For braiding as well as for filament winding the angle, in which the fiber is placed on the core, varies strongly with a changing diameter. Fig. 3 shows a general dependence between radius and fiber angle.

Fig. 3. Analytical connection between core radius and fiber angle

Changing process parameters can influence this, but the tendencies will stay the same. With decreasing diameter the fiber angle will strongly increase for

filament winding. However for the braiding process it means, that the fiber angle decreases (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Fiber angle in relation to the radius for filament winding and braiding

For modeling the winding software ISAWIND® [4] is modified, in order to build up the pressure vessel's laminate rapidly. Therefore equation 1 is implemented to take the braiding fiber lay down paths into account. It correlates *the fiber angle* α (on the mandrel surface in the axis direction) with the *mandrel radius* r and the machine parameters *take-up speed* v_m and *angular velocity of the carrier* ω_c [5]:

$$\alpha = \arctan \frac{\omega_c \cdot r}{v_m} \quad (1)$$

The vessel has a diameter of 200 mm in the cylindrical section; the diameter of the polar openings is 70 mm. For hydrogen tanks with a working pressure of 70 MPa high burst pressure of 164.5 MPa must be reached which can only be resisted by a thick-walled composite laminate. This causes stress gradients throughout the laminate;

therefore layered solid elements are used for the finite element model (Fig. 5).

It is assumed, that the overbraiding is done with a constant take-up and bobbin speed. This results in a uniform braiding angle in the cylindrical section and a decreasing braiding angle in the domes.

To adjust the fiber direction according to the applied pressure loads, different braiding angles in the cylindrical section as well as variations of the laminate design were examined.

The braiding angles and layer thicknesses were analytical determined with a specifically programmed calculation tool. The data were transferred to ISAWIND®, allowing the generation of a solid element mesh for the finite element simulation; including the information specific to the braiding process (Fig. 4).

Fig. 5. Finite element model of the overbraided pressure vessel

For the material data of the laminate standard parameters of a 12k intermediate modulus carbon fiber and epoxy resin were used. These material parameters were decreased with factors derived from literature of braided coupon tests as well as experience data from filament wound vessels. Additionally a polymeric liner and metallic end boss were modeled for the finite element simulation. The testing calculations were performed under static internal pressure load of 164.5 MPa.

Layer-by-layer post-processing was executed in a spreadsheet program. For this purpose, the stress values along the local fiber direction were exported from the finite element results and compared with the strength of the composite material in fiber direction (Fig. 7).

4 Results

Filament wound pressure vessels have a typical shape in the dome section. This shape is optimized for the lay-up patterns of the winding process, based on an isotenoid contour [3]. On the basis of conservative material properties for the braided laminates, no configuration could be found, that ensures the required safety against failure without extensive layer adding. Hence, modifications to the dome contour must be made, considering the different lay-up path of a braided structure.

Figure 7 shows the evaluation of typical simulation results. The path-coordinate extends in meridian direction along the overbraided surface. Two critical values were defined, one for the maximum tension allowed in the cylindrical section of the vessel, the second one for the maximum tension in the dome area.

To obtain a laminate for the vessel, that can withstand the required pressure loads, layers in the cylindrical section were added. This showed that the most critical parts, concerning loads that would lead to failure, were in the dome for most of the cases. This is due to stress gradients caused by the thick-walled laminate and the curvature discontinuity at the transition from the cylindrical part to the dome. By varying the braiding angles as well as the laminate stacking the maximum stresses in the dome area could be decreased. However a reduction to a non-critical value could not be achieved, under the condition that the weight should not be higher than for a typical filament wound vessel.

Fig. 6. Shapes of the dome contours in sectional view

To further decrease the maximum tension in the fibers a second optimization approach was chosen by varying the contour shape of the domes. Originally characteristic dome geometry of a filament wound vessel was chosen. As already presented in Fig. 4, the fiber angles differ strongly depending on the used production process. To fulfill the braiding process's fiber angle characteristic a prolonged contour shape was chosen.

After various iterations, the maximum tension in the fibers could be decreased to a level beneath the failure tension. This was achieved without adding any further laminate layers. The contour shape was then closer to a circular contour.

Figure 6 shows the modified dome contour that is used in order to design a braided pressure vessel, which is able to withstand pressures similar to filament wound vessels, whilst having an equal weight.

Gravimetric and storage density were used to compare the vessel. This was necessary due to the different geometries of the domes, thus being able to set a relation between different resulting volume and the weight resulting from the amount of carbon composite used.

The storage density showed slightly better results for the braided pressure vessels in comparison to the filament wound pressure vessels. Focusing on the processes itself, in braiding a multitude of fibers can be guided onto the core simultaneously. The braiding machine used at ITA braids 144 fiber strands simultaneously, compared to four to ten rovings or tows that are wound in a standard filament winding process. This results in a lower machine occupation time.

Fig. 7. Tension in fiber direction under pressure

5 Discussion

Lightweight pressure vessels made from carbon fiber reinforced materials can be used for hydrogen storage in automotive applications. Nowadays these vessels are produced through filament winding.

The presented results show, that braiding is a reasonable alternative approach to filament winding. A concept has been developed to simulate a braided pressure vessel, analog to well known and established design procedures of a filament wound vessel.

Important parameters for the design and simulation are machine parameters, fiber properties and vessels geometry. The differences in the production process lead to diverse fiber angles. These fiber angles are used as an input for the finite element simulation. Fibers mainly take up loads in their longitudinal direction. Hence the aim was to adapt the fiber angle to the load direction as much as possible. The research showed that the dome contours for braided pressure vessel have to be adapted to the process for being able to take the loads.

The simulation shows that braided vessels can compete to filament wound vessels considering material usage as well as storage density. A shorter production time is an advantage for braided vessels.

The work in this paper presents how modeling techniques from filament wound pressure vessels can be transferred to braided structures. It also underlines that the braiding process is a highly potential alternative to filament winding of high-pressure vessels.

Each fiber roving on its own is slower fed to the mandrel in the braiding process. However in braiding multiple fiber strands are braided simultaneously. The machine considered for the process braids up to 144 fiber strands at the same time, whereas in filament winding usually only up to 10 strands are deposited in parallel. This results in an estimated decrease of production time of up to 30%.

Fig. 8. Overview of the research project structure

Not only the laminate has to be adjusted to meet the expected pressure, but also the shape in the dome region.

Filament wound pressure vessel show a progressively increasing fiber angle towards the dome end. A braided structure has the opposite tendency. This results in a dome shape that must decrease less fast in its diameter. The final shape is closer to a circular shape.

A final comparison between storage densities of filament wound and braided pressure vessels showed a slight advantage towards the braided production approach. However, this result depends on the assumed fiber strength translation efficiency for the braided structure that has to be verified by experiments.

The open questions from the simulation will be addressed in further research as depicted in Fig. 8. The assumed fiber paths for the simulation were based on an analytical formula. Real braiding parameters differ from this theoretical assumption. These fiber paths will be examined in tests on a

braiding machine. Furthermore data from a detailed process simulation for the braiding process will be used as input for the structural simulation. Material tests will be performed on characteristic braiding structures to determine the laminate properties. With that information an extensive lightweight optimization of dome contour shape and laminate structure can be carried out. Finally a full-scale demonstrator will be produced.

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